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M3.8 - Technical EOSC PID Implementation Guide & Program

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Practical PID Guide for National Initiatives

This guide is intended for organisations, groups or consortiums planning to implement a national level PID policy, strategy or set of recommendations.

Recommendations from the RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist (2023)
Ensure you have:

- A clear value proposition with use cases
- A group or organisation that is responsible for driving strategy development
- An open, inclusive, iterative process that involves all stakeholders
- An accompanying roadmap that outlines practical steps for implementation

Define the concrete actions and processes

What actions are needed and what does the overall process look like for the creation and approval of the PID strategy?

Plan the process. Think about what group or organisation is responsible for driving strategic development. Keep this process open, inclusive and iterative and ensure that it involves all stakeholders. Create an accompanying roadmap that outlines the practical steps for implementation.

Engage with relevant stakeholders

Consider how to engage with different stakeholders for the creation of your national PID strategy. Organise national-level workshops and open consultations to get feedback on the work.

Monitor and/or measure compliance

Consider how you will monitor and/or measure the success of the strategy, e.g., through impact reporting. Consider implementing a monitoring mechanism for PID uptake and implementation.

STEP

1

Consider your drivers and capabilities

What are the main drivers for the national PID strategy? Assess your mandate and identify the stakeholders you need to involve in the strategy consultation phase as well as the target groups of the PID strategy.

What is the preliminary scope of the strategy? You can expand or limit the scope in later steps.

STEP

2

Implement selected tools, methods and approaches

Create a draft action plan including resources needed. Conduct a landscape analysis as a first step and choose the tools to be used for the creation and future updates of the PID strategy as well as review and approval of the national PID strategy. Consider the update frequency of the strategy. Think about the structure of the strategy including a clear value proposition with use cases and an accompanying roadmap that outlines practical steps for implementation.

STEP

3

STEP

4

Ensure uptake of implemented PID strategy

How do you ensure that stakeholders understand their role and the needed actions on the roadmap? How do you build up to the required capacity among stakeholders? Create an engagement strategy.

STEP

5

STEP

6

Practical PID Guide for Service Providers

This guide is intended to assist and inspire service providers within the European research domain who require integrations with a PID service(s) to improve the FAIRness, openness and utility of their offerings.

Involvement of stakeholders and identification of their role

Identify your main stakeholder(s). It is crucial to understand both your direct user base's needs as well as their obligations to governing bodies (e.g. EOSC and federal data management policies). Your stakeholders may also expand beyond your direct user base. We recommend mapping all your stakeholders to the various roles within the PID stack.

Furthermore, PIDs are a socio-technical infrastructure and will likely require your stakeholders to commit to owning and maintaining the (meta)data within PIDs for a long time. Involve them early and establish clear roles, responsibilities and a governance structure for PID management.

For more information about stakeholder roles see R14 in the attached References document. For guidance on drafting PID strategy and policy see R1 and for examples of national and organisational level strategies and policies see R6-R13.

Select a PID Service(s)

Deciding what kind of PIDs and which PID service provider(s) to obtain them from is a crucial step in setting up PIDs for your service. All the factors noted in the previous steps can help decide what kind of PIDs to employ.

Any PIDs used should be globally unique and persistently resolvable (a.k.a. GUPRI). You must also consider cost and your budget, both in terms of implementation and maintenance. Additionally, you should verify that the PID service is trustworthy and has sound policies in place. The policies should be in line with your service's needs and your community's expectations. There are different contract models for PIDs and depending on your budget and needs, you must contemplate the most suitable choice for you.

In addition to these considerations, it is also important that you are aware of how exactly the setup will work. Do you need only the PIDs themselves to be hosted or also the metadata? Will you hold the metadata on your own landing page and what will that look like? At this point the right questions should be asked and the design decisions from previous steps need to be validated.

For more resources to help you select your PID stack, see R2-R5 in the attached References document.

Advanced Policy Development

Develop and publish all the policies required to sustain a long-term and reliable service. This can include:

- PID service decommission/migration plan
- Policies for the deletion/tombstoning of individual PID records
- Establishment of minimum contract lengths and user obligations to ensure persistence
- Versioning schemas for PIDs and policy around PIDs (including updates)
- Proof of compliance with other policies e.g. EOSC PID policy, RDA, national, userbase's institutional policies, security protocols, GDPR, intellectual property laws, etc.

STEP 1

Define what your PIDs will identify

Persistent identifiers can identify people (e.g. researchers), places (e.g. research organizations) and things (e.g. research outputs such as publications, datasets, samples, instruments, etc.). It is essential that your organisation and user base not only defines what resources they seek to attach PIDs to but also at what scale you will be generating PIDs (e.g. a thousand per year vs a million per year), what added-value/quality enhancing features PIDs bring to your service, the direct benefits for your user base, what corresponding metadata will need to be coupled with the resources and how they will version changes to the resources.

STEP 2

Identify PID visibility requirements

When integrating PIDs into a service you need to contemplate how and when end users will interact with the PIDs. Will end users need to be aware they are interacting with a PID or will they simply click on a link and wait for it to resolve to the resource as is commonly the case with DOIs and journal articles? Additionally PIDs require a corresponding metadata schema and metadata record. These can be machine-readable and/or human-readable. Machine-readable metadata ensures that systems can process, index, and retrieve resources efficiently, supporting automated workflows and discoverability. Human-readable metadata is essential for providing context, clarity, and understanding to users, enabling them to evaluate the relevance of a resource. Identify and provide the minimum metadata records that caters for this need.

STEP 3

STEP 4

Integrating PIDs in your system

An essential question is how the PIDs will be integrated into your service, especially if you are using PIDs as subfields of your data or metadata (e.g., a DOI as a reference in an article or sub-fields such as a RAiD which can contain an ORCID or ROR ID). Will these PIDs be validated? Will (federated) authentication be needed? What tools (e.g. APIs) are necessary for the setup to work and are they available? This can be even more complicated if there is sensitive data or data with restricted access involved.

STEP 5

STEP 6

Monitoring the PID service(s)

Once everything is up and running, you want to make sure that your system is working as designed and is maintained properly. Make sure that you know beforehand what the SLAs of your PID service provider(s) are with regards to availability and resolvability. This should be aligned with what your service requirements and the PID service(s) should be held accountable to it. You can set up a monitoring system to track this data. This is of course in addition to your and your user base's obligation to maintain the accuracy and currentness of the data that the PIDs refer to.

STEP 7

Legend

Design focused step

Policy focused step

Technically focused step

Practical PID Guide for Institutions

This guide is intended to assist and inspire institutions who have the responsibility to maintain the integrity of the relationship between entities (such as datasets, publications, and researchers) and their persistent identifiers. Examples are 'handles' for datasets, 'DOIs' for publications and 'ORCIDs' for researchers. Institutions in this respect are assigned the role of "PID managers": they must ensure that the persistent identifiers remain linked to the object or concept being referenced.

A number of guidelines and steps directed at institutions have been distinguished (see R14). The most prominent ones that an institution (in the role of PID manager) MUST follow are detailed here.

Manage Persistence

Institutions must develop policies and procedures to guarantee the maintenance of the correct link between the identifier and the resolution target, and make sure the responsibilities are well defined in their agreements or contracts with the PID owner. The two main culprits of lack of persistence are "link rot" (where the web link does not resolve to a resource) and "content drift" (where the web link does not refer to the resource it was initially connected to).

Select an appropriate scale

Institutions (acting as PID managers) must consider the scale at which PIDs will be used - this can range from hundreds (for research outputs) to hundreds of millions (for graph-like nodes and relations with versioning and authenticity). Two interrelated considerations are: scalability of the service and the cost. Also future migration and annual growth should be considered.

Develop and implement sustainability and continuity mechanisms

Institutions (acting as PID managers) must develop and implement mechanisms to ensure continued access should their services need to wind down or change and preferably have access to sustainable funding. If applicable, certification as a trustworthy repository helps ensure that adequate measures are in place.

STEP

1

Select a PID Stack that is globally unique and persistently resolvable

Select a PID Stack with persistence, uniqueness, and resolution characteristics appropriate to the use case. For this, the acronym GUPRI can be used: the PID must be Globally Unique, Persistent with a Resolvable Identifier.

For more resources to help you select your PID stack, see R2-R5 in the attached References document.

STEP

2

Manage Versions

Institutions (acting as PID managers) must have a clear policy on version management. The provisions of the policy depend on the purpose of referencing resources by the persistent identifier. The semantics of versioning principles may be aligned with good practice as used in the versioning of software [R15] and adapted as follows:

- "Major" version when you make changes that do not support reproducibility
- "Minor" version when you add content in a reproducibility-compatible manner
- "Patch" version when you make backward compatible improvements

STEP

3

STEP

4

Maintain resolution integrity

Institutions (acting as PID managers) must maintain the link between the identifier and its resolution mechanism, and the object or concept being referenced. In most cases, Managers offer custom metadata for the object or concept that is authoritative, and this MUST be maintained. Tombstones MUST be offered in cases where objects or concepts are no longer available, based on rational cases.

STEP

5

STEP

6

Develop and implement sustainability and continuity mechanisms

Institutions (acting as PID managers) must develop and implement mechanisms to ensure continued access should their services need to wind down or change and preferably have access to sustainable funding. If applicable, certification as a trustworthy repository helps ensure that adequate measures are in place.

References

The following references are used across 3 infographics, “Practical PID Guide for National Initiatives”, “Practical PID Guide for Institutions” and “Practical PID Guide for Service Providers”.

No	Description/Link
R1	Brown, C., Simons, N., Bangert, D., & Sadler, S. (2023). RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist (1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091
R2	Lahtinen, A., Lukkarinen, A., Koivula, H., Liimatainen, J. O., Parland-von Essen, J., Tana, J., Koiranen, J., Hakala, J., Herrala, J., Pajari, J., Hakkila, K., Hilska-Keinänen, K., Nissin, L., Karlsson, L., Kuusniemi, M. E., Vuorinen, M., Frosterus, M., Kaarakainen, M.-T., Salminen, N.-M., ... Pääkkönen, T. (2020). Choosing and implementing persistent identifiers : Guide for research organisations. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4395767
R3	Madden, F., van Horik, R., van de Sandt, S., Lavasa, A., & Cousijn, H. (2020). Guides to Choosing Persistent Identifiers - Version 3 (Version 3). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4192174
R4	Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed. (n.d.). A Guide to Choosing PIDs for Heritage Institutions. https://www.pidwijzer.nl/en/
R5	Parland-von Essen, J., Alaterä, T., Sipola, T., Lukkarinen, A., Pääkkönen, T., Kiiskinen, H., Aalto, T., Kaurahalme, O.-P., Salminen, N.-M., Lötjönen, S., Pajari, J., Hakkarainen, J.-P., & Silander, K. (2019). The use of Persistent Identifiers for Research Datasets : Recommendation by the Finnish Scientific Community for Open Research (1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3560738
R6	Akcaova, G., Slot, P., de Smaele, M., Hoogerwerf, M., Sesink, L., Baars, C., de Jong, M., Coombs, S., van de Sanden, M., & Voorburg, R. (2022). Towards a national PID roadmap. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5849310
R7	Cruz, M., & Tatum, C. (2021). NWO Persistent Identifier Strategy (Version 2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4695367
R8	A national persistent identifier research strategy - Jisc. (2024, October 15). Jisc. https://www.jisc.ac.uk/innovation/projects/a-national-persistent-identifier-research-strategy

R9	PID Forum Finland (2024, April 1). The National Roadmap for Persistent Identifiers for Finland. Doria. https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2024032512910
R10	Hausstein, B., & Horton, L. (2022). CESSDA ERIC Persistent Identifier Policy 2022 (2.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6607000
R11	Madden, F. (2021, 11 November). The British Library Adopts a New Persistent Identifier Policy. Digital Scholarship Blog. https://blogs.bl.uk/digital-scholarship/2021/11/the-british-library-adopts-a-new-persistent-identifier-policy.html
R12	Australian Research Data Commons. (2024). Australian national Persistent Identifier (PID) strategy 2024. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10656276
R13	ORFG PID Strategy Working Group. (2024). Developing a US National PID Strategy. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10811008
R14	van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2024). D3.3 - Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC Compliant PID Policy (V2.0 - DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14092489
R15	Preston-Werner, T. (n.d.). Semantic Versioning 2.0.0. Semantic Versioning. https://semver.org/

Glossary

Where applicable, selected definitions are reproduced here from the *EOSC Glossary (2020)*. Other definitions were supplemented from internal documents.

Access Policy: policy defining the obligations for authorizing access to a resource.

[SOURCE: ISO 27789:2013, modified – reference to policy]

Actor: individual or group that fulfills one or more roles in the EOSC. **EXAMPLE:** A research performing organisation participating in the EOSC initiative as a service provider and as an end-user.

API: set of commands, functions and protocols that specify how software components should interact.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18598:2016]

Content drift: the web link within a PID does not refer to the resource it was initially connected to.

FAIR principles: set of guiding lines to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

[SOURCE: COMMISSION DECISION of 27.8.2018 Setting up the Expert Group - Executive Board of the European Open Science Cloud ('EOSC') and laying down rules for its financing.]

GUPRI: Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifier.

Human-readable: in a form that is clear and can be easily understood by a human reader.

Link rot: the web link does not resolve to a resource within a PID.

Machine-readable: in a form that can be identified, recognised and extracted by a computer.

[SOURCE: CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary . <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/> , modified – reference to identified, recognised and extracted instead of used and understood.]

Metadata: data defining and describing other data.

Note 1 to entry: Metadata can be categorised as descriptive, structural, preservation and

administrative metadata.

[SOURCE: ISO 8000-2:2020, modified – Note 1 to entry has been added; ISO/TR 14873:2013, modified – reference to preservation metadata.]

Open science: approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge.

[SOURCE: Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing Horizon Europe -the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, 11251/1/20 REV 1. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/45766/st11251-re01-en20.pdf>]

PID manager: user who has responsibilities to maintain the integrity of the relationship between digital objects and their PIDs , in conformance to a PID scheme defined by a PID authority.

Note 1 to entry: A PID manager will typically subscribe to PID services to offer functionality to PID owners within the PID manager's services. One example is a service provider which uses PID Services as part of its own service delivery. For example, PID managers may include a provider of a data repository , a data catalogue, or a research workflow System.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud , modified – reference to user; reference to digital objects instead of entities.]

PID owner: user who has the authority to create a PID , assign PID to a digital object , provide and maintain accurate kernel information for the PID.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud , modified – reference to user instead of actor; reference to digital object instead of entity]

PID scheme: set of rules and standards defining the nature of a PID.

Note 1 to entry: This would include a set of lexical formatting rules for PIDs within a namespace. It could also define for example: associated PID type; definition of associated metadata; quality assurance conditions; usage rights, terms and conditions, and algorithmic methods for generating PID names and enforcing PID properties.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud .]

PID service: IT service that create, manage and resolve PIDs and their associated kernel information which conforms to a PID scheme.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud , modified – reference to IT service.]

PID service provider: service provider which provides PID services in conformance to a PID scheme, subject to its PID authority.

Note 1 to entry: PID service providers have responsibility for the provision, integrity, reliability and scalability of PID services, in particular the issuing and resolution of PIDs, but also lookup and search services, and interoperability with a generic resolution system.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud , modified – reference to service provider instead of organisation.]

PID Stack: The collection of services and actors, supported by standardisation, resolution mechanisms, and namespace management that results in a branded or unique PID Service to PID Managers.

Policy: documented set of intentions, expectations, goals, rules and requirements, often formally expressed by top management representatives in an organisation or federation .

Note 1 to entry: Policies are then realised in processes , which are in turn made up of activities that people carry out according to defined procedures.

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). FitSM-0: Overview and Vocabulary .
<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/> .]

Service level agreement (SLA): service contract that defines measurable conditions of interactions between a service provider and an end-user .

Note 1 to entry: A service level agreement may specify: the set of services the service provider will deliver, a sufficient, specific definition of each service, the responsibilities of the service provider and the end-user, the set of metrics to determine whether the service provider is delivering the service as promised, an auditing mechanism to monitor the service, the remedies available to the end-user and service provider if the terms of the SLA are not met, and how the SLA will change over time.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to end-user instead of service consumer.]

Stakeholder: actor that can affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by a decision or activity.

EXAMPLE Customers, owners, people in an organization , providers , bankers, regulators, unions, partners or society that can include competitors or opposing pressure groups.

[SOURCE: ISO 9000:2015, modified – Note 1 to entry has been removed; reference to actor instead of person or organization.]

User base: the group of stakeholders using the provided service.

Value-added service: service that is offered in addition to the core service in question thus creating additional value.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 24760-1:2019]

Work Cited

EOSC Glossary Interest Group. (2020). EOSC Glossary (December 2020). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4472643>